

Supplementary information

Evaluating lithium recovery using electrochemical membrane separation: cost analysis and design strategies

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Table S1. Nomenclature. Related to Methods.

Symbol	Description	Units
i_{lim}	Limiting current density	A/m ²
i_i	Partial current density for ion i	A/m ²
i_t	Total current density	A/m ²
F	Faraday constant	C/mol e ⁻
R	Molar gas constant	J/K·mol
T	Temperature	K
Z_i	Charge number for ion i	mol e ⁻ / mol i
D_i	Ion diffusivity for ion i	m ² /s
D_{eff}	Multi-ion diffusivity of the brine	m ² /s
r_{st}	Recovery factor in the stack	unitless
k_{eff}	Mass transfer coefficient	m/s
t_i	Transference number for ion i	unitless
M_i	Molar weight for ion i	g/mol
$S_{i/j}$	Membrane binary selectivity for ion i vs ion j	unitless
ρ_{Li}	Area resistance of Li-selective membrane	$\Omega \cdot m^2$
ρ_{an}	Area resistance of anion exchange membrane	$\Omega \cdot m^2$
κ_f	Specific electrical conductivity of the feed stream	$\Omega^{-1} \cdot m^{-1}$
κ_{ex}	Specific electrical conductivity of the extract stream	$\Omega^{-1} \cdot m^{-1}$
Rc	Area resistance of electrochemical cell	$\Omega \cdot m^2$
L_f	Filament size of the spacer	m
h	Channel thickness	m
Δx	Mesh step of the spacer	unitless
ε	Channel voidage	unitless
ξ	Current utilization in the stack	unitless
β	Shadow factor in the stack	unitless
$C_i^{in.f}$	Weight concentration of ion i in the feed brine	g/m ³
$C_i^{av.f}$	Average weight concentration of ion i in the feed stream	g/m ³
$C_i^{r.f}$	Weight concentration of ion i in the Li-reduced stream	g/m ³
$C_i^{av.f.m}$	Average molar concentration of ion i in the feed stream	mol/m ³
C_i^{en}	Weight concentration of ion i in the Li-enriched stream	g/m ³
$C_i^{av.ex.m}$	Average molar concentration of ion i in the extract stream	mol/m ³
j	Superscript j denotes the stage number	unitless
$S_{\bar{i}}^{\bar{j}}$	Binary selectivity between ion i and j	unitless

$\bar{S}_{i/(j.k)}$	Mean value selectivity between ion i, and ions j and k	unitless
μ	Brine dynamic viscosity	Kg/m·s
ρ	Brine density	Kg/m ³
g	Gravitational acceleration (~9.81)	m/s ²
u	Superficial average flow velocity	m/s
W	Total width of Li-selective membrane	m
L	Total length of Li-selective membrane	m
A_m	Li-selective membrane area	m ²
Δp_f	Pressure drop in the feed side of the stack	Kg/m·s ²
Δp_{ex}	Pressure drop in the extract side of the stack	Kg/m·s ²
Δp_{max}	Maximum stack pressure drop limit	Kg/m·s ²
σ_m	Tensile strength of the ion exchange membrane	Kg/m·s ²
f	Darcy friction coefficient	unitless
Q_f	Volumetric flow rate in the feed side of the stack	m ³ /s
Q_{ex}	Volumetric flow rate in the extract side of the stack	m ³ /s
$E_{st.Pr}$	Energy consumption for stack pressure adjustment	kWh
E_{RC}	Energy losses from resistance and voltage drop	kWh
$n_{Li.ex}$	Li extraction capacity	g/s
r_{ch}	Recovery factor in the Li ₂ CO ₃ recovery stage	unitless
$C_{p.ch}$	Heat capacity of solution in recovery stage	kg/s
ρ_{ch}	Density of solution in recovery stage	Kg/m ³
R_{ch}	Carbonate to lithium molar ratio in recovery stage	mol/mol
N	Plant life cycle	years
IR	Interest rate	unitless
η	Pump efficiency	unitless
K_{Li}	Li-selective membrane price	USD/m ²
K_{an}	Anion exchange membrane price	USD/m ²
K_{st}	Stack price	USD/m ²
K_u	Electricity price	USD/kWh
$K_{Na_2CO_3}$	Price of sodium carbonate	USD/ton
α_f	Amortization factor	unitless
MRF	Membrane replacement factor	unitless
Sh	Sherwood number	unitless

Sc	Schmidt number	unitless
Re	Reynolds number	unitless
y	Plant availability	unitless
D_{off}	Distance of intake source from pump station	m
H	Distance of intake source from water surface	m
T_{Li}	Amortized cost of Li membrane investment + replacement cost	USD
T_{an}	Amortized cost of anion exchange membrane investment + replacement cost	USD
T_{st}	Amortized cost of stack capital expenditure and auxiliary equipment	USD
T_{pr}	Energy cost for stack pressure adjustment	USD
T_{rc}	Energy cost from cell resistance and voltage drop	USD
T_{in}	Pre-stack intake and pretreatment cost	USD
T_{disch}	Brine discharge cost	USD
T_{main}	Plant maintenance cost	USD
T_{labor}	Labor cost	USD
$T_{in.con}$	Pre-stack intake construction cost	USD
$T_{disch,con}$	Brine discharge construction cost	USD
$T_{in.pre}$	Pre-stack pretreatment construction cost	USD
T_{ch}	Lithium carbonate recovery expenses	USD
T_{El}	Electrochemical process cost	USD
$T_{in.con.E}$	Pre-stack intake energy cost	USD
$T_{in.pre.E}$	Pre-stack pretreatment energy cost	USD
$T_{rec.En}$	Energy cost for lithium carbonate recovery stage	USD
$T_{rec.ch}$	Chemical expenditure costs in recovery stage	USD

Note S1. Intake, pretreatment, and disposal costs. Related to Methods.

In this work, the intake and pretreatment costs were evaluated based on formulas and information available for seawater desalination plants. Both intake and pretreatment stages include capital expenditures (capex) related to construction costs and operational expenditures (opex) related to energy costs.

The intake stage is a crucial component of seawater desalination plants, and the type and location of the intake source significantly impact the construction costs. Open offshore intakes are preferred for larger capacity plants to ensure consistent water quality and minimize operational disturbances. The distance from the onshore pump station can vary between 300 to 2000 meters, and the vertical distance from the intake point can range from 8 to 24 meters below the water surface^{1,2}. For lithium extraction from seawater in this work, an offshore distance of 500 meters and an average depth of 10 meters below the sea surface were considered. For other brine sources, such as salt lakes and salars, an average distance of 100 meters from the pump station and a vertical distance of 5 meters were assumed, as these sources often allow for closer proximity of the plant to the water source. It is important to note that these are assumptions and may vary depending on the specific water source.

For both intake and pretreatment stages, universal plots are available for estimating capex related to construction costs (Figure S1). These plots provide cost estimates as a function of volumetric flow rate, which for lithium extraction is determined by the source lithium concentration.

Figure S1. Construction cost for intake and pretreatment stages as a function of volumetric flow rate. Related to Methods

- (A) Construction costs for the intake stage.
- (B) Construction costs for the pretreatment stage.

The equations were derived using polynomial regression analysis from universal plots. For intake conduit construction, the choice of construction material (HDPE or concrete) depends on plant capacity. For membrane pretreatment, the equations were derived to cover the medium cost bracket. The figures are adopted from ref¹.

Accordingly, the intake and pretreatment construction costs can be evaluated using the following equations derived through polynomial regression analysis from the universal plots:

$$T_{in.con} = \frac{(((14040 \times Q_f) + 15000) \times D_{off}) \times \alpha_f}{(365 \times y)} \quad (\text{eq. S1})$$

$$T_{in.pre} = \frac{((-366.5 \times Q_f^2) + (7550 \times Q_f) + 1073) \times \alpha_f}{(365 \times y)}, \quad Q_f \leq 2.77 \quad (\text{eq. S2})$$

$$T_{in.pre} = \frac{((6383.29 \times Q_f) + (1588)) \times \alpha_f}{(365 \times y)}, \quad Q_f > 2.77 \quad (\text{eq. S3})$$

Where the amortization factor (α_f) to account for payback period is calculated based on the applied interest rate (IR) and plant life cycle (N):

$$\alpha_f = \frac{IR \cdot (IR+1)^N}{(1+IR)^N - 1} \quad (\text{eq. S4})$$

The energy cost for the brine intake is evaluated based on the distance of the intake source from the water surface:

$$T_{in.con.E} = \left(\frac{(Q_f \cdot \rho \cdot g \cdot H)}{(1000 \times \eta)} \times 24 \times K_u \right) \quad (\text{eq. S5})$$

The energy cost for the pretreatment stage was derived from ref ³, which reported an average energy requirement of 0.3 kWh per cubic meter of seawater for the pretreatment by membrane filtration process:

$$T_{in.pre.E} = (Q_f \cdot 3600 \cdot 24 \cdot 0.3) \times K_u \quad (\text{eq. S6})$$

For wholesale electricity (K_u), a value of 0.077 USD/kWh was considered as the average value from market data⁴.

Since nearly the same flow rate must be returned to the source, the construction cost for surface water disposal of the de-lithiated stream was estimated based on the intake construction cost:

$$T_{disch} = T_{disch.con} = T_{in.con} \quad (\text{eq. S7})$$

Thus, the overall cost of the intake, pre-treatment and brine disposal costs can be evaluated as follows:

$$T_{in} = T_{in.pre.E} + T_{in.con.E} + T_{in.pre} + T_{in.con} + T_{disch} \quad (\text{eq. S8})$$

Note S2. Membrane and material costs in the electrochemical process. Related to Methods

The material costs in the electrochemical process consist of the following components: the cost of Li selective membrane investment plus replacement cost (T_{Li}), the cost of anion exchange membrane investment plus replacement cost (T_{an}), and the cost of stack capital expenditure and auxiliary equipment (T_{st}).

The required amount of Li selective membrane area can be evaluated by mass balance considering the desired extraction rate and limiting current density as follows:

$$A_m = \frac{n_{Li,ex} \cdot F \cdot Z_{Li}}{r_{ch} \cdot \xi \cdot \beta \cdot i_{lim} \cdot M_{Li}} \quad (\text{eq. S9})$$

where, $n_{Li,ex}$ denotes the desired extraction rate and r_{ch} is the recovery factor in lithium carbonate recovery stage. Shadow factor (β) accounts for the part of the membrane inaccessible for the current due to spacers, and current utilization (ξ) is a factor relating to inefficiencies caused by non-desired phenomena such as water transport through the membrane and current leakage through the manifold, as well as other non-selectivity's such as co-ion transport⁵.

The limiting current can be evaluated by the following expression⁶:

$$i_{lim} = (Z_{Li} \cdot F) \times \left(\frac{D_{Li}}{D_{eff}} \right) \times K_{eff} \times C_{Li}^{av.f.m} \quad (\text{eq. S10})$$

the average Li molar concentration in the feed stream can be calculated by:

$$C_{Li}^{av.f.m} = \frac{C_{Li}^{av.f}}{M_{Li}} \quad (\text{eq. S11})$$

$C_{Li}^{av.f}$ is expressed by the log mean concentration⁷ in the feed stream:

$$C_{Li}^{av.f} = \frac{C_{Li}^{in.f} - C_{Li}^{r.f}}{\ln \left(\frac{C_{Li}^{in.f}}{C_{Li}^{r.f}} \right)} \quad (\text{eq. S12})$$

By mathematical arrangement $C_{Li}^{av.f.m}$ can be expressed based on the recovery factor in the stack:

$$r_{st} = \frac{C_{Li}^{in.f} - C_{Li}^{r.f}}{C_{Li}^{in.f}} \quad (\text{eq. S13})$$

and we have:

$$C_{Li}^{av.f.m} = \frac{C_{Li}^{in.f} \cdot r_{st}}{M_{Li} \cdot \ln \left(\frac{1}{1-r_{st}} \right)} \quad (\text{eq. S14})$$

The relation between limiting current density and design parameters (channel height (h), width-to-length ratio (W/L), and spacer mesh size (L_f) is established through the correlations for boundary layer mass transfer coefficient (K_{eff}). Mass transfer coefficient is related to hydrodynamic factors through dimensionless Reynolds (Re) and Schmidt number (Sc):

$$K_{eff} = Sh \times \frac{D_{eff}}{h} = a \cdot Re^b \cdot Sc^c \quad (\text{eq. S15})$$

Reynolds and Schmidt numbers can be evaluated from flow properties and cell geometry:

$$Re = \frac{D_h u \rho}{\mu} \quad (\text{eq. S16}) \quad \text{and} \quad Sc = \frac{\mu}{\rho D_{eff}} \quad (\text{eq. S17})$$

Where the hydraulic diameter (D_h) and superficial flow velocity (u) are direct function of flow velocity and cell geometry:

$$D_h \sim 2 \cdot h \quad (\text{eq. S18}) \quad \text{and} \quad u = \frac{Q_f}{W \cdot h} \quad (\text{eq. S19})$$

The mass transfer correlations have the empirical form and constants a , b , and c vary depending on hydrodynamic conditions⁸.

In this work we borrowed mass transfer (Sh) and friction factor (f) correlations from the seminal works of Isaacson and Sonin⁹, Kuroda et al.¹⁰, and Wright et.al¹¹ who presented the correlations for electro dialysis systems with careful experimental support. The key correlations used at different conditions are summarized below:

$$Re \leq 50$$

$$Sh = 0.29 \times Re_d^{0.5} \times Sc^{1/3} \quad , \quad Re_d = \frac{Re}{e} \quad , \quad e = 1 - \left(\frac{0.4}{\Delta x}\right) \quad , \quad \text{and} \quad \Delta x = \left(\frac{L_f}{h}\right) \quad (\text{eq. S20})^{11}$$

$$f = 4 \times \frac{40.37}{e^{5.35} Re} \quad (\text{eq. S21})^{11}$$

$$50 \leq Re \leq 700 \quad , \quad 3 \leq \frac{L_f}{h} \leq 10 :$$

$$Sh = 0.86 \times Re^{0.5} \times Sc^{1/3} \times \sqrt{\frac{2 \cdot h \cdot e}{0.00153}} \quad (\text{eq. S22})^{10}$$

$$f = 4 \times \frac{0.0557 \times \sqrt{2 \cdot h \cdot e}}{e \cdot Re^{0.5} \cdot L_f^{0.119} \cdot h} \quad (\text{eq. S23})^{10, 11}$$

$$700 \leq Re \leq 2800 \quad , \quad \frac{L_f}{h} = 2:$$

$$Sh = 0.39 \times \left(\frac{Re}{2}\right)^{0.62} \times Sc^{1/3} \quad (\text{eq. S24})^9$$

$$f = \frac{176}{\left(\frac{Re}{2}\right)} + 0.57 \quad (\text{eq. S25})^9$$

$$800 \leq Re \leq 2800 \quad , \quad \frac{L_f}{h} = 4:$$

$$Sh = 0.12 \times Re^{0.80} \times Sc^{1/3} \quad (\text{eq. S26})^9$$

$$f = \frac{99}{\left(\frac{Re}{2}\right)} + 0.29 \quad (\text{eq. S27})^9$$

$$800 \leq Re \leq 2000 \quad , \quad \frac{L_f}{h} = 16:$$

$$Sh = 0.45 \times Re^{0.51} \times Sc^{1/3} \quad (\text{eq. S28})^9$$

$$f = \frac{42}{\left(\frac{Re}{2}\right)} + 0.107 \quad (\text{eq. S29})^9$$

$$800 \leq Re \leq 1600, \quad \frac{L_f}{h} = 31:$$

$$Sh = 0.75 \times Re^{0.38} \times Sc^{1/3} \quad (\text{eq. S30})^9$$

$$f = \frac{34}{\left(\frac{Re}{2}\right)} + 0.058 \quad (\text{eq. S31})^9$$

As observed, Isaacson and Sonin report the correlations only for certain integer values ($\Delta x = 2, 4, 16,$ and 31) of mesh steps. Thus, to be able to cover the ranges between these values, we used a linear interpolation method. This approach was justified by the mostly linear behavior observed between the Sherwood number and the Reynolds number within the explored range ($800 \leq Re \leq \sim 2000$ and $2 \leq \Delta x \leq 31$, see the work of Isaacson and Sonin). Note that all these studies considered net type spacers with an attack angle of 90° .

The capital expenditure for the investment in Li-selective membranes and the operational expenditure for the replacement of these membranes can be evaluated based on the required amount of Li-selective membrane (A_m).

$$T_{Li} = \frac{K_{Li} \cdot A_m \cdot (MRF + \alpha_f)}{365 \cdot y} \quad (\text{eq. S32})$$

The required amount of anion exchange membrane will be equal to that of the Li-selective membrane, and the corresponding cost for the anion exchange membrane can be evaluated using a similar formula:

$$T_{an} = \frac{K_{an} \cdot A_m \cdot (MRF + \alpha_f)}{365 \cdot y} \quad (\text{eq. S33})$$

with the maintenance and replacement factor (MRF) assumed to be the same for both types of membranes. The price for the anion exchange membrane is based on an estimated cost of approximately 125 USD/m² ^{5, 12}.

The stack capital expenditure and auxiliary equipment complementary to the electrochemical process can be derived based on the total area of ion exchange membranes and by applying a multiplication factor to the price of ion exchange membrane^{12, 13}:

$$T_{st} = 2 \times \left(\frac{K_{an} \cdot (2 \times A_m) \cdot (MRF + \alpha_f)}{365 \cdot y} \right) \quad (\text{eq. S34})$$

Note S3. Energy costs in electrochemical process. Related to Methods.

The energy costs in the electrochemical process consist of the following components: the energy cost related to stack pressure drop (T_{pr}), and energy cost from cell resistance and voltage drop (T_{rc}). Below, we will find relevant expressions for these terms under steady state limiting current operation.

Pressure loss in the feed channel of the electrochemical stack can be evaluated by Darcy-Weisbach equation:

$$\Delta p_f = f \times \frac{L}{h} \times \frac{u^2}{2} \times \rho \quad (\text{eq. S35})$$

Where f is the Darcy friction factor defined by Isaacson and Sonin⁹. And L is related to Li selective membrane rea through following relation:

$$L = \left(\frac{A_m}{W} \right) \quad (\text{eq. S36})$$

We assumed identical operative pressure (pressure losses) in the feed and extract channels. This is a common practice in commercial ED stacks to avoid pressure differences between the two streams^{11, 14}, which can be achieved by adjusting the flow velocities on both sides. Nonzero trans-membrane pressure can cause water transport and hydraulic fluxes through the ion exchange membrane, reducing current utilization and lowering extraction efficiency¹². Therefore, the pressure loss in the extract channel is assumed to be equal to that in the feed channel:

$$\Delta p_{ex} = \Delta p_f \quad (\text{eq. S37})$$

Accordingly, the energy cost for the stack pressure adjustment can be obtained by the following expression:

$$T_{pr} = E_{st.Pr} \times K_u \quad (\text{eq. S38})$$

$$E_{st.Pr} = \frac{Q_f \cdot \Delta p_f \cdot 24}{(1000 \cdot \eta)} + \frac{Q_{ex} \cdot \Delta p_{ex} \cdot 24}{(1000 \cdot \eta)} \quad (\text{eq. S39})$$

The multiplication factor (24/1000) converts the result to kWh consumed per day.

The volumetric flow rate in the extract stream (Q_{ex}) can be calculated based on the desired lithium extraction capacity ($n_{Li,ex}$), target Li concentration in the recovery stage (C_{Li}^{en}), and recovery factor (r_{ch}):

$$Q_{ex} = \frac{n_{Li,ex}}{r_{ch} \cdot C_{Li}^{en}} \quad (\text{eq. S40})$$

The energy related to cell resistance and voltage drop consists of two components. The first component relates to the overall electrical resistance of the electrochemical stack, which arises from the resistance of the bulk feed and extract solutions, as well as the resistance of the ion exchange membranes. The second component is the additional energy required to compensate for the negative lithium concentration gradient across the lithium-selective membrane.

The overall area resistance of the electrochemical cell (including both the feed and extract channels) can be calculated as follows:

$$Rc = \rho_{Li} + \rho_{an} + \frac{h}{\kappa_f} + \frac{h}{\kappa_{ex}} \quad (\text{eq. S41})$$

The specific electrical conductivities of the feed (κ_f) and extract streams (κ_{ex}) can be obtained from the following expressions¹⁵:

$$\kappa_f = \frac{F^2}{R \cdot T} \times (D_{Cl} \cdot C_{Cl}^{av.f.m} + D_{Na} \cdot C_{Na}^{av.f.m}) \quad (\text{eq. S42})$$

$$\kappa_{ex} = \frac{F^2}{RT} \times (D_{Cl} \cdot C_{Cl}^{av.ex.m} + D_{Li} \cdot C_{Li}^{av.ex.m}) \quad (\text{eq. S43})$$

These expressions assume that sodium and chloride are the major ions contributing to the bulk conductivity of the feed stream, and lithium and chloride are the major ions contributing to the bulk conductivity of the extract stream (see source data for Figure 4 in the supplemental information).

The energy consumption to compensate for overall resistance of the cell is obtained by Ohm's law:

$$E_{RC} = (i_t \cdot A_m)^2 \times \frac{Rc}{A_m} \times \frac{24}{1000} \quad (\text{eq. S44})$$

Where $i_t = \frac{i_{lim}}{t_i}$ (eq. S45) defines the total current density based on limiting current density and Li transference number.

Under limiting current operation and steady state conditions, the concentration of lithium ions in the extract stream increases, while that in the feed stream decreases along the channel length. The buildup of lithium ions in the extracted stream creates a negative chemical potential gradient across the lithium-selective membrane (Figure S2). Due to the operational mode at a fixed current density (constant extraction rate along the flow stream), this negative chemical potential gradient cannot be compensated by back diffusion of lithium ions (unless we assume leakage to other cations or co-ions through Li selective membrane), resulting in additional cell potential drop.

This additional potential drop can be approximated assuming a rapid attainment of equilibrium balance of counter-ions at the membrane-solution interfaces. The Donnan potential (ψ_D) is a term to characterize the equilibrium balance of the exchange ion and is expressed as the potential difference between the membrane (ψ_m) and the solution (ψ_s) at the interface and can be calculated based on ion activity ratios^{16, 17}.

Figure S2. Chemical potential gradient along the channel. Related to Methods.

Schematic illustrating the buildup of a chemical potential gradient along the channel ($X = 0 \rightarrow X = L$), caused by increasing the Li concentration in the extract stream and decreasing Li concentration in the feed stream.

The Donnan potential at the feed side of the Li selective membrane can be expressed as follows:

$$\psi_D^f = \psi_m^f - \psi_s^f = \frac{RT}{z_{Li}F} \times \text{Ln} \left(\frac{\gamma_{Li}^{s.f} \cdot C_{Li}^{s.f}}{\gamma_{Li}^{m.f} \cdot C_{Li}^{m.f}} \right) \quad (\text{eq. S46})$$

And the Donnan potential at the extract side of the Li selective membrane is:

$$\psi_D^{ex} = \psi_m^{ex} - \psi_s^{ex} = \frac{RT}{Z_{Li}F} \times \ln\left(\frac{\gamma_{Li}^{s,ex} \cdot C_{Li}^{s,ex}}{\gamma_{Li}^{m,ex} \cdot C_{Li}^{m,ex}}\right) \quad (\text{eq. S47})$$

where $\gamma_{Li}^{s,f}$ and $\gamma_{Li}^{s,ex}$ are the activity coefficients of Li ions in the corresponding solutions phases, and $\gamma_{Li}^{m,f}$ and $\gamma_{Li}^{m,ex}$ are the activity coefficients of Li ions in the Li selective membrane. $C_{Li}^{s,f}$ and $C_{Li}^{s,ex}$ are the Li ion concentrations in the solution phases, and $C_{Li}^{m,f}$ and $C_{Li}^{m,ex}$ are the Li ion concentrations in the membrane phase. As in the previous equations, *f* denotes the feed side and *ex* denotes the extract side of the cell. Assuming equality of ion activity coefficients in each phase¹⁸ and negligible concentration and potential gradient inside the membrane, the electrical potentials of bulk solutions can be related as follows:

$$\psi_s^f - \psi_s^{ex} = \frac{RT}{Z_{Li}F} \times \ln\left(\frac{C_{Li}^{s,ex}}{C_{Li}^{s,f}}\right) \quad (\text{eq. S48})$$

Therefore, the energy consumption caused by the negative Li concentration gradient can be approximated with the following equation:

$$E_{Con} = (i_t \cdot A_m) \times \frac{RT}{Z_{Li}F} \times \ln\left(\frac{C_{Li}^{av,ex,m}}{C_{Li}^{av,f,m}}\right) \times \frac{24}{1000} \quad (\text{eq. S49})$$

And overall energy cost from cell resistance and voltage drop is obtained:

$$T_{rc} = (E_{Con} + E_{Rc}) \times K_u \quad (\text{eq. S50})$$

In addition to the cost components mentioned above, labor and maintenance costs were also included, and estimated based on the work of Generous et al.¹³ for the desalination plants:

$$T_{labor} = 0.05 \times Q_f \times 24 \times 3600 \quad (\text{eq. S51})$$

$$T_{main} = 0.02 \times \left[\left(\frac{K_{Li} \cdot A_m \cdot (\alpha_f)}{365 \cdot y} \right) + \left(\frac{K_{an} \cdot A_m \cdot (\alpha_f)}{365 \cdot y} \right) + \left(2 \times \left(\frac{K_{an} \cdot (2 \times A_m) \cdot (\alpha_f)}{365 \cdot y} \right) \right) \right] \quad (\text{eq. S52})$$

Eq. S52 considers the maintenance cost as a multiplication factor of total direct capital costs of membrane and stack investments. Thus the replacement factor is removed from the equation.

Thus, the overall electrochemical process cost can be obtained as sum of energy costs and material costs:

$$T_{El} = T_{rc} + T_{pr} + T_{Li} + T_{an} + T_{st} + [T_{labor} + T_{main}] = T_{rc} + T_{pr} + T_{Li} + T_{an} + T_{st} + T_{labor,main} \quad (\text{eq. S53})$$

The various material components of the electrochemical process (eq. 53) are related to the lithium-selective membrane area and the limiting current density. These parameters can be optimized through improvements in flow velocity and cell geometry (eqs. S15-S19). However, there are trade-offs involved in this optimization. Due to the inverse relationship between the friction factor and Reynolds number, and the direct relationship between pressure drop, flow velocity, and the overall length of the membrane, optimizing the membrane area can simultaneously increase the pressure drop. Additionally, another energy term inversely affected by membrane area optimization is the energy related to the overall cell resistance (eq. S44). The complex relationships between various energy and material terms necessitate a careful optimization process to determine the optimal design parameters as a function of other input variables, as described in the main text.

Note S4. Lithium carbonate recovery, Related to Methods.

There are two opex terms involved in the Li_2CO_3 recovery stage. One is related to the use of Na_2CO_3 as a reagent, and the other is the energy input required for the temperature-driven precipitation reaction. The precipitation conditions were assumed to be 80°C and a 1:1 carbonate / lithium ratio¹⁹. The energy cost can be obtained as follows:

$$T_{rec.En} = \left(\frac{n_{Li.ex} \cdot 24}{r_{ch} \cdot C_{Li}^{en}} \cdot \rho_{ch} \cdot C_{p.ch} \cdot \Delta T \right) \times K_u \quad (\text{eq. S54})$$

And the expenses caused by chemical expenditure can be obtained based on the market price of sodium carbonate ($K_{\text{Na}_2\text{CO}_3}$) and the set carbonate / lithium ratio (R_{ch}):

$$T_{rec.ch} = \left(\frac{n_{Li.ex} \cdot 24 \cdot 3600}{r_{ch} \cdot M_{Li}} \cdot R_{ch} \cdot M_{\text{Na}_2\text{CO}_3} \right) \times \frac{K_{\text{Na}_2\text{CO}_3}}{(1000000)} \quad (\text{eq. S55})$$

And average price of 200 USD/ton was assumed for sodium carbonate²⁰. The overall cost of chemical recovery stage is then obtained as follows:

$$T_{ch} = T_{rec.En} + T_{rec.ch} \quad (\text{eq. S56})$$

Note S5: Mg^{2+} and Ca^{2+} leakage. Related to Methods.

The binary selectivity's for Li^+ versus Mg^{2+} and Ca^{2+} are defined as follows:

$$S_{\frac{Li}{Mg}} = \frac{C_{Li}^{en} / C_{Mg}^{en}}{C_{Li}^{in.f} / C_{Mg}^{in.f}} \quad (\text{eq. S57})$$

$$S_{\frac{Li}{Ca}} = \frac{C_{Li}^{en} / C_{Ca}^{en}}{C_{Li}^{in.f} / C_{Ca}^{in.f}} \quad (\text{eq. S58})$$

The ratio of Li to Mg weight concentrations in the Li enriched stream (the extract stream at the outlet of the cell) in stage j can be described based on corresponding partial current densities:

$$\frac{C_{Li}^{en.j}}{C_{Mg}^{en.j}} = \frac{i_{Li}^j}{i_{Mg}^j} \times \frac{Z_{Mg}}{Z_{Li}} \times \frac{M_{Li}}{M_{Mg}} = \frac{t_{Li}^j \times i_t^j}{t_{Mg}^j \times i_t^j} \times \frac{Z_{Mg}}{Z_{Li}} \times \frac{M_{Li}}{M_{Mg}} = \frac{t_{Li}^j}{t_{Mg}^j} \times \frac{Z_{Mg}}{Z_{Li}} \times \frac{M_{Li}}{M_{Mg}} \quad (\text{eq. S59})$$

where i_{Li}^j and i_{Mg}^j are partial currents for Li and Mg transport in stage j , and i_t^j is the corresponding total current in the same stage. Similarly, for Li and Ca, we have:

$$\frac{C_{Li}^{en.j}}{C_{Ca}^{en.j}} = \frac{i_{Li}^j}{i_{Ca}^j} \times \frac{Z_{Ca}}{Z_{Li}} \times \frac{M_{Li}}{M_{Ca}} = \frac{t_{Li}^j \times i_t^j}{t_{Ca}^j \times i_t^j} \times \frac{Z_{Ca}}{Z_{Li}} \times \frac{M_{Li}}{M_{Ca}} = \frac{t_{Li}^j}{t_{Ca}^j} \times \frac{Z_{Ca}}{Z_{Li}} \times \frac{M_{Li}}{M_{Ca}} \quad (\text{eq. S60})$$

By definition, the transference numbers sum to unity:

$$t_{Li}^j + t_{Mg}^j + t_{Ca}^j = 1 \quad (\text{eq. S61})$$

With further mathematical manipulation, we arrive at the following expression for the transference number of Li in stage j:

$$T_{Li}^j = \frac{\left(\left(\frac{S_{Li}}{Mg} \right)^j \times D_{Li/Mg} \right)}{1 + \left(\frac{S_{Li}}{Mg} \right)^j \times D_{Ca/Mg} + \left(\frac{S_{Li}}{Mg} \right)^j \times D_{Li/Mg}} \quad (\text{eq. S62})$$

where:

$$D_{Li/Mg} = \frac{c_{Li}^{in.f}}{c_{Mg}^{in.f}} \times \frac{z_{Li}}{z_{Mg}} \times \frac{M_{Mg}}{M_{Li}} \quad (\text{eq. S63})$$

$$D_{Ca/Mg} = \frac{c_{Ca}^{in.f}}{c_{Mg}^{in.f}} \times \frac{z_{Ca}}{z_{Mg}} \times \frac{M_{Mg}}{M_{Ca}} \quad (\text{eq. S64})$$

The weight ratios of Li/Mg and Li/Ca in the outlet of the extract stream of the stage j can be related to the corresponding weight ratios at the inlet to the first stage:

$$\frac{c_{Li}^{en.j}}{c_{Mg}^{en.j}} = \left(\frac{S_{Li}}{Mg} \right)^j \times \frac{c_{Li}^{in.f}}{c_{Mg}^{in.f}} \quad (\text{eq. S65})$$

$$\frac{c_{Li}^{en.j}}{c_{Ca}^{en.j}} = \left(\frac{S_{Li}}{Ca} \right)^j \times \frac{c_{Li}^{in.f}}{c_{Ca}^{in.f}} \quad (\text{eq. S66})$$

Accordingly, the minimum required number of asymmetric stages to achieve the desired level of solution purity (target Li/Mg and Li/Ca weight ratios for efficient Li_2CO_3 recovery) is determined by the following expression:

$$n = \max(n1, n2) \quad (\text{eq. S67})$$

where:

$$n1 = \log_{\frac{S_{Li}}{Mg}} \left(\left(\frac{c_{Li}}{c_{Mg}} \right)_{target} \times \frac{c_{Mg}^{in.f}}{c_{Li}^{in.f}} \right) \quad (\text{eq. S68})$$

$$n2 = \log_{S_{\frac{Li}{Ca}}} \left(\left(\frac{C_{Li}}{C_{Ca}} \right)_{target} \times \frac{C_{Ca}^{inf}}{C_{Li}^{inf}} \right) \quad (\text{eq. S69})$$

Under circumstances when Ca and Mg ions have similar mobilities in the membranes- for example, close mobilities for Ca and Mg reported in nanoporous membranes ^{21, 22} - the individual binary selectivity's may be replaced by a mean value:

$$\bar{S}_{Li/(Ca.Mg)} = av \left(S_{\frac{Li}{Mg}}, S_{\frac{Li}{Ca}} \right) \quad (\text{eq. S70})$$

Then, the number of stages will be determined by the compound (Ca or Mg) that has the larger content relative to Li in the brine feed. In the evaluation of stages for scenarios involving both Mg and Ca leakage, a mean selectivity value was considered in this work.

Note S6. Inequality constraints. Related to Methods.

The inequality constraints imposed on the optimization process in this work were derived from process and design considerations (see source data for Figure 4 in the supplemental information) to ensure that variables remained within physically meaningful and operationally feasible ranges. The constraints within the optimization process included the upper and lower boundaries for the channel thickness (h) and the spacer mesh size (Δx), as well as pressure drop limit. These constraints, along with other inequality criteria considered during the post-evaluation stage, are summarized as follows:

$$u \leq 250 \quad \left(\frac{cm}{s} \right) \quad (\text{eq. S71})$$

$$0.1 \leq h \leq 10 \quad (mm) \quad (\text{eq. S72})$$

$$2 \leq \Delta x \leq 31 \quad (-) \quad (\text{eq. S73})$$

$$L \geq 0.5 \quad (m) \quad (\text{eq. S74})$$

Another important constraint was to maintain the maximum Reynolds number (Re) below 1600. This was necessary due to the lack of valid mass transport correlations for spacer-filled electro dialysis channels with Re numbers beyond this threshold. However, the optimization process revealed that the optimal Re number always remained below this value, even without imposing this constraint. This is because higher flow velocities result in increased pressure drops, which are associated with higher costs.

$$Re \leq 1600 \quad (\text{eq. S75})$$

Inequality constraints for Re , u , and L were applied during the post-evaluation stage to simplify the optimization process. This allowed the solver to focus on optimizing the design variables while ensuring the final solutions satisfied these additional criteria.

Note S7. Membrane tensile strength as additional constraint. Related to Methods.

To ensure the integrity of the membrane during operation and prevent rupture or deformation due to the stress caused by the pressure drop along the stack, the membrane was operated within conditions that

would not generate stresses exceeding its tensile strength. The rupture threshold can be evaluated by the following equation:

$$\Delta P_{max} = \frac{\sigma_m \cdot L}{h} \quad (\text{eq. S76})$$

Where σ_m denotes the membrane tensile strength and ΔP_{max} denotes the pressure drop limit equivalent to rupture threshold.

Figure S3. Electrochemical process cost for various brine sources and different Li membrane prices. Related to Figure 4 in results and discussion.

The figure illustrates the electrochemical process cost for producing 1 ton of LCE per day along with optimal design parameters. Data are presented based on the minimum cost obtained from optimal design parameters for each combination of brine source and Li membrane price. Brines are grouped based on their Li concentration, and other physical properties (viscosity, density, effective diffusivity, and specific electrical conductivity) were averaged within each group for analysis. Details of the brine data can be found in the Source Data for Figure 4. Assumptions include a Li transference number of 1 and stack pressure drop limit of 150 bar.

Li Membrane Price: 20000 (USD)/m²

Li Membrane Price: 40000 (USD)/m²

Figure S4. Cost analysis of Li₂CO₃ production (1 ton of LCE per day) through an optimized electrochemical Li recovery process. Related to Figure 5 in results and discussion.

The bubble plots show how different cost components of Li₂CO₃ production vary with membrane price and brine Li concentration. Each column corresponds to a specific Li concentration and each row to a distinct cost component. Within each column, bubble size is proportional to that component's contribution for the given brine. For visual clarity, seawater-related costs were scaled down by a factor of 200, and costs for other brines were scaled down by a factor of 5 prior to plotting. For example, for seawater at a membrane price of 500 USD/m², the total process cost is 200×2200 USD per ton of LCE, while for a brine with 22 ppm Li at the same membrane price it is 5×1030 USD per ton of LCE. Other components in each column can be scaled using the same factors. The right-hand subplots show the percentage contribution of each component for the corresponding membrane price. The costs associated with stack pressure drop adjustment and cell resistance reflect the overall energy consumption of the electrochemical process (measured in kWh multiplied by the energy price). Assumptions include a Li transference number of 1 and stack pressure drop limit of 150 bar. Detailed values of costs and energy consumption can be found in Source Data for Figure 5.

Note S8. Recovery ratio and limiting current fraction as process variables. Related to Results and discussion.

Figure S5 illustrates the impact of the recovery ratio (0.15–0.85) and the limiting current fraction (0.4–1) on the process cost for a representative brine containing 41 ppm Li. The limiting current fraction represents a proportion of the limiting current density determined by optimization process. Both the recovery ratio and the limiting current fraction were varied within the optimization process, without external manipulation.

Figure S5. Impact of recovery ratio and limiting current fraction on process cost. Related to Results and discussion.

(A) Effect of the limiting current fraction and (B) effect of the recovery ratio as process variables on the overall cost of extracting 1 t of Li₂CO₃ per day. Variations in the recovery ratio initially decrease the process cost to a minimum, after which the cost increases. This behavior is attributed to higher intake and pretreatment costs resulting from the increased total flow rate at lower recovery ratios.

Figure S6. Recovery ratio and its impact on pressure drop and process costs. Related to Results and discussion.

The figure illustrates the increase in process costs and pressure drop as the recovery ratio decreases for a representative brine containing 41 ppm Li, with a membrane price of 12,500 USD/m². The W/L ratio, h , and L_f were held constant across the range of recovery ratios.

Note S9. Validation and Sensitivity Analysis. Related to Methods.

Table S2 compares the results obtained from the multi-start *fmincon* optimization with those from a hybrid *surrogateopt-fmincon* approach for six representative cases. All cases exhibited a 1-2% deviation between the two optimization methods, indicating consistency in identifying the global or near-global minima.

Table S2. Comparing results from multi-start *fmincon* approach with those of hybrid *surrogateopt-fmincon* approach.

Brine composition, membrane price	$(h_{fmincon}/h_{hybrid})$	$(L_{f,fmincon}/L_{f,hybrid})$	$(\frac{W}{L})_{fmincon} / (\frac{W}{L})_{hybrid}$	$(\frac{Cost_{fmincon}}{Cost_{hybrid}})$
41 ppm, 500 USD/m ²	1.0000	1.0024	0.9995	1
41 ppm, 40000 USD/m ²	0.9953	0.9953	1.014	1.0004
0.17 ppm, 500 USD/m ²	1.0001	1.0000	1.0001	1.0000
0.17 ppm, 40000 USD/m ²	1.0000	0.9785	1.0212	0.9937
710 ppm, 500 USD/m ²	1.0100	0.9389	0.9845	1.0000
710 ppm, 40000 USD/m ²	0.9803	1.1816	0.9841	0.9985

To assess the reliability of the optimization routine in identifying the design variables that correspond to the true minimum process cost, a sensitivity analysis was conducted for three representative brine compositions: 0.17 ppm Li, 41 ppm Li, and 710 ppm Li. Each case was analyzed using a membrane price of 12,500 USD/m². Two sets of contour plots were generated for each case. In the first set (shown on the right side of Figure S7), the variables *Wt* and *h* were varied while keeping *Lf* fixed at the optimal value obtained from the multi-start **fmincon** optimization. In the second set (shown on the left side of the figure), *h* and *Lf* were varied while *Wt* was held constant at its respective optimal value. The resulting contour plots include detailed annotations of the cost values and corresponding design variables within each region. The locations of the minimum cost and the associated design configurations matched closely with those identified by the optimization routine. This agreement confirms the robustness and accuracy of the multi-start **fmincon** results in capturing the global minimum in the design space.

Li concentration: 0.17 ppm, Membrane price: 12500 USD/m², Optimal flow width (m): 53148.74
 [Solutions: sensitivity analysis]/ [Solutions: optimization process]:
 Electrochemical process cost (USD/t Li₂CO₃): [1238204] / [1202847]
 Spacer mesh size (mm): [0.7]/ [0.69]
 Channel thickness (mm): [0.17]/ [0.17]

Li concentration: 0.17 ppm, Membrane price: 12500 USD/m², Optimal spacer mesh size (mm):0.7
 [Solutions: sensitivity analysis]/ [Solutions: optimization process]:
 Electrochemical process cost (USD/t Li₂CO₃): [1238204] / [1202847]
 Channel thickness (mm): [0.17]/ [0.17]
 Flow width (m): [53000]/ [53148]

Li concentration: 41 ppm, Membrane price: 12500 USD/m², Optimal flow width (m): 163.88
 [Solutions: sensitivity analysis]/ [Solutions: optimization process]:
 Electrochemical process cost (USD/t Li₂CO₃): [6420] / [6418.4]
 Spacer mesh size (mm): [0.97]/ [0.98]
 Channel thickness (mm): [0.241]/ [0.244]

Li concentration: 41 ppm, Membrane price: 12500 USD/m², Optimal spacer mesh size (mm):0.98
 [Solutions: sensitivity analysis]/ [Solutions: optimization process]:
 Electrochemical process cost (USD/t Li₂CO₃): [6422] / [6418]
 Channel thickness (mm): [0.241]/ [0.244]
 Flow width (m): [163]/ [163.8]

Figure S7. Evaluation of Model Performance for the Optimization Process. Related to Methods.

The figure presents contour plots illustrating the variation in total process cost with respect to key design parameters for three representative brine compositions. **Left panels:** Variation of process cost as a function of channel thickness (h) and spacer mesh size (L_f), with flow width (W_t) fixed at its optimal value from the optimization. **Right panels:** Variation with respect to flow width (W_t) and channel thickness (h), holding spacer mesh size (L_f) at its optimized value. Text boxes above graphs display the optimal values obtained from both the *multi-start fmincon* optimization and the sensitivity analysis. The close agreement between the two supports the optimization results.

**Li concentration: 710 ppm, Membrane price: 12500 USD/m²,
 Optimal flow width (m): 8.1**
 [Solutions: sensitivity analysis]/ [Solutions: optimization process]:
 Electrochemical process cost (USD/t Li₂CO₃): [1403.1] / [1403.02]
 Spacer mesh size (mm): [2.87]/ [2.86]
 Channel thickness (mm): [0.72]/ [0.717]

**Li concentration: 710 ppm, Membrane price: 12500 USD/m²,
 Optimal spacer mesh size (mm):2.87**
 [Solutions: sensitivity analysis]/ [Solutions: optimization process]:
 Electrochemical process cost (USD/t Li₂CO₃): [1403.34] / [1403.02]
 Channel thickness (mm): [0.72]/ [0.717]
 Flow width (m): [8]/ [8.1]

Figure S7. Evaluation of Model Performance for the Optimization Process. Related to Methods.

The figure presents contour plots illustrating the variation in total process cost with respect to key design parameters for three representative brine compositions. **Left panels:** Variation of process cost as a function of channel thickness (h) and spacer mesh size (L_f), with flow width (W_t) fixed at its optimal value from the optimization. **Right panels:** Variation with respect to flow width (W_t) and channel thickness (h), holding spacer mesh size (L_f) at its optimized value. Text boxes above graphs display the optimal values obtained from both the *multi-start fmincon* optimization and the sensitivity analysis. The close agreement between the two supports the optimization results.

Note S10. Optimization flow diagram. Related to Methods.

Note S11. Mg recovery as a side process. Related to Results and discussion.

Table S3 reports relative changes in process cost when Mg recovery was considered from the Li-depleted stream. A selling price of 1000 USD/t for MgCO₃ was assumed and deducted from the total process cost to calculate the relative change. Positive values indicate an increase in overall cost (i.e., the process becomes more expensive even after accounting for Mg revenue), while negative values indicate a reduction in total process cost due to the added value from Mg sales.

Table S3. Relative changes in the overall process cost for Li₂CO₃ extraction when MgCO₃ production is integrated.

Brine composition (41 ppm)	<i>Membrane price: 500 USD/m²</i>	<i>Membrane price: 5000 USD/m²</i>	<i>Membrane price: 12500 USD/m²</i>
<i>Mg/Li ratio:65</i>	-7.028%	+2.94%	+6.62%
<i>Mg/Li ratio: 2.4</i>	+3.88%	+29.36%	+41.93%
<i>Mg/Li ratio:0.058</i>	+684%	+1516%	+1882%
Brine composition (160 ppm)			
<i>Mg/Li ratio:65</i>	-10.21%	+5.01%	+13.46%
<i>Mg/Li ratio:2.4</i>	-7.711%	+8.6%	+21.27%
<i>Mg/Li ratio:0.058</i>	+226%	+632%	+1079%
Brine composition (411 ppm)			
<i>Mg/Li ratio:65</i>	-11%	+5.58%	+16.18%
<i>Mg/Li ratio:2.4</i>	-9.8%	+18.12%	+17.21%
<i>Mg/Li ratio:0.058</i>	85.3%	+292%	+501.3%

Figure S8. Sensitivity analysis for MRF. Related to Conclusions.

This figure illustrates the relative increase in overall process cost for a brine with 41 ppm Li content as a function of the membrane replacement factor (MRF). A higher MRF corresponds to a shorter membrane lifespan, leading to increased membrane replacement frequency and, consequently, higher overall process costs.

Note S12. Impact of larger plant capacity. Related to Results and discussion.

Figure S9 shows the relative changes in process cost due to deviation from the optimal channel thickness for various plant production capacities, using the representative case of brine with 41 ppm Li and a membrane price of \$5000/ m². As observed, the sensitivity to the optimal design parameter becomes more pronounced at higher plant capacities, particularly when increasing from 1 ton per day to 10 tons per day. Table S4 provides detailed values of optimal design parameter for the different plant capacities under the same scenario.

Figure S9. Sensitivity Analysis of Optimal Channel Thickness for Different Plant Capacities. Related to Results and discussion.

This figure illustrates the relative increase in overall process cost for brine containing 41 ppm Li, assuming a Li membrane price of \$5000/ m², as a function of deviations in channel thickness from its optimal value. The left panel shows negative deviations, while the right panel shows positive deviations relative to the optimal channel thickness. The other two design parameters (W/L ratio and Lf) are held constant.

Table S4. Changes in the overall process cost and optimal design parameters for Li₂CO₃ production at different plant capacity.

Total process costs and optimal design parameters	<i>1 ton LCE/day</i>	<i>10 ton LCE/day</i>	<i>100 ton LCE/day</i>
<i>Total Process Cost (USD)</i>	6495	54024	528000
<i>Channel thickness (μm)</i>	330	347	327
<i>Mesh size (mm)</i>	1.32	1.38	1.31
<i>W/L ratio (dimensionless)</i>	61	540	6194

Note S13. Sensitivity of design parameters and electrochemical process costs to mass transport correlations. Related to Results and discussion.

Table S5 presents the sensitivity of stack design parameters and electrochemical process costs to variations in the mass transport correlations. The analysis considers $\pm 10\%$ and $\pm 20\%$ changes in the multiplicative coefficient (f) and the Reynolds-number exponent (g) in Eqs. S20–S30. Here, f denotes the multiplicative coefficient and g the Reynolds-number exponent in all relevant Sherwood correlations, as illustrated in the universal form in eq. S77. Positive and negative shifts were applied symmetrically to evaluate the impact on each parameter.

$$Sh \sim f \times Re^g \times Sc^{1/3} \quad (\text{eq. S77})$$

Table S5. Sensitivity of stack design parameters and electrochemical process costs to changes in mass transport correlations.

Case	Channel thickness (μm)	W/L (dimensionless)	Mesh size (mm)	Electrochemical process costs (USD)
Base case	330	61	1.32	4018
+10 % shift in f	328	68	1.31	3705
-10 % shift in f	326	56	1.30	4401
+20 % shift in f	334	71	1.33	3448
-20 % shift in f	327	49	1.30	4883
+10 % shift in g	462	46	1.84	2709
-10 % shift in g	104	2004	0.416	4738
+20 % shift in g	1498	6.7	5.96	1871
-20 % shift in g	100	1707	0.40	5658

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